

FLORAL DECORATIVE ELEMENTS EXECUTED ON THE CERAMICS OF KHEIWA AND KHOKAND

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The Central Asian region left us with a long history of cultural heritage in many areas, and it is considered one of the richest regions of the Islamic world in Islamic antiquities, which varied between mosques, schools, palaces, burial domes, castles, and others, which date back to the various historical periods that the region has gone through since the entry and spread of Islam there. The region was also distinguished by its production of many applied antiques, which varied between ceramic products, wood, stone and marble works, textiles, and carpets. This is evidenced by what abounds in the Uzbek and Russian museums, international museums, and some private collections of many artistic antiques produced by artists in the region, especially the period of the two centuries (12. - 13 AH / 18/19 AD), some of which have been studied, while a large portion has not reached the hands of researchers. Therefore, I chose to study one of the applied arts produced by craftsmen in the Khokand and Khiva khanates, represented by ceramic artifacts, through studying the preserved collections. In the museums of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other international museums and private collections under the title “Ceramic vessels in the Khanates of Kokand and Khiva, the beginning of the 12th century AH until the middle of the 14th century AD, the beginning of the 18th century AD until the middle of the 20th AD,” an artistic archaeological study.

The period of the 13th century AH / 19AD is considered one of the most prosperous historical periods in the manufacture of many applied arts specific to the Khanate region, during which various industries flourished, including the ceramic industries. The prosperity of this industry is indicated by the huge amount of products preserved by the Uzbek and Russian museums and some international museums, in contrast to the other periods. Previous historical information has been provided to us through historical sources indicating the prosperity of this industry, but only a little of it has reached us, and studying it is not enough to identify the technical features and characteristics that distinguish the periods of its production.

Decorative elements on ceramic vessels in Kokand and Khiva since the 12th century AH until the middle of the 14th century AH / 18AD until the middle of the 20th century AD.

The ceramic industries in the Uzbekistan region passed through various stages between prosperity, distinction and mastery, and other periods of decline and

stagnation, especially in the period The 11th - 12th centuries AH / 17-18AD), and this is due to the multiplicity of states and emirates in Uzbekistan and their preoccupation with military conflicts among them, which had a negative impact on the arts and their production, while industries, including the ceramic industry, rose again and became more beautiful and complex than any previous period. This occurred at the beginning of the 13th century AH / 19th century AD (1).

When looking at the decorations of ceramic vessels in Khokand and Khiva, we notice the great similarity between the decorations of these vessels and the decorations of their counterparts produced in Bukhara. This may be due to the fact that since the end of the 13th century AH / 19 AD and the beginning of the 14th century AH / 20 AD many Khorezmian craftsmen and artists have studied Art at the hands of the famous masters in Bukhara, which led to the development of decorations executed on the products in Khiva, and new artistic features appeared on them closer to the city of Bukhara. Therefore, we find that there is a great similarity between the artistic products in Khiva and their counterpart in Bukhara - (Y). The artistic styles and methods have varied. Which the artist used in decorating ceramic artifacts, including drawing over the paint as well as under the paint, in addition to decoration by using the method of engraving and slitting, Plate No. (169) (170), stamping, and decorations executed with the mold. However, the most common decorative methods used in implementing decorations on ceramic artifacts are The subject of study is the method of implementing decorations by drawing under transparent glaze.

The most common colors used in implementing the various decorative elements on the ceramic vessels subject of the study were white, blue, green, and brown in shades. The most widespread type in Central Asian ceramics during the period under study was ceramics painted under paint.

The decorative elements executed on the ceramics of the city of Khiva varied between various floral, geometric, and written decorations, as well as decorations containing drawings of buildings and decorative architectural elements, and others containing human drawings and personal pictures.

The following is a presentation of some distinctive examples of ceramic vessel decorations that were produced in Kokand and Khiva between the 12th century AH: 18 AD (14 AH: 20 AD). First: Floral Decorations Floral decorations received appreciation and attention in all arts, and were dominant in Islamic art. This may be due to the depth of the Muslim artist's faith, his sensitivity, the tenderness of his feelings, and his love for the nature around him that he contemplated, which led him to invent new forms of floral decorations that distinguished art. Islamic distinction from other arts.

By plant decoration, we mean every adornment or decorative ornament that is based, in its drawing or engraving, on plant elements such as stems, leaves, flowers, and fruits in their various shapes and forms, whether they are in their natural form or modified from nature (2). Plant decorations played an important role in the decoration of various types of applied arts, whether in the city of Khiva or its neighboring cities, including, for example, ceramic artifacts produced by the city of Tashkent of various types in the period under study. Modified and realistic plant decorations appeared, and it was dominated by Some of these floral decorations have Iranian influences.

Plant decorations played a prominent role in the decoration of the ceramic vessels that are the subject of the study. They were the most common, widespread, and used decorative elements on those vessels. The artist used their various elements, such as branches, leaves, and flowers, a wide scope in occupying the decorative spaces on his various ceramic products, and one of their most decorative elements is It was widespread and used not only in Khanate Khiva, but in the three khanates, Bukhari, Khokand, Khiva are the modified floral decorations, "arabesques" (1) known to them as "Islami", which were widely used on various artistic products, such as ceramic vessels and tiles, and marble and stone works. Woodwork, metal products, and textiles, especially "Susana

Palm fans were used as a floral decorative element in abundance on various types of applied antiques produced in the Central Asian region during the period under study. They were found on many of the ceramic products under study, plates with numbers, on metals, and on textiles.

The plant branches played an important role in the decoration of ceramic artifacts in their various forms, which were produced during the period under study in the Central Asian cities neighboring Khiva, including Bukhara, Samarkand, Tashkent, Shahraziz, and Rashtan, whether they were individual plant branches from which emanated plant leaves and rosettes that adorned the frames that adorned those artifacts, or branches interwoven in a complex manner that decorate larger areas

Plant leaves :They are one of the important elements of plant decoration. Hardly any plant decorative design is devoid of drawings of plant leaves of various types. The plant branch, and the plant leaves take on different appearances and shapes, including simple ones and some complex ones. The artist excelled in matching the size and shape of the plant leaf with the space in which it is occupied. The potter also succeeded in linking those plant leaves with other elements of plant decoration, such as branches and flowers, and creating a balance In ceramic pots.

The serrated leaves have many forms. They are either half serrated, which are serrated leaves on one side, or half serrated, which are serrated leaves on both sides.

Spear-shaped leaves, plates. They are simple plant leaves, characterized by their length being greater than their width, their base being broad, and their tip retracting to a pointed apex. They are executed either singly, or emerging from simple or compound branches. , wavy or straight

Flower drawings: They are among the botanical decorative elements that have spread widely and abundantly in the decoration of various branches of applied arts produced in the Central Asian region. This may be due to the artist's love and fondness for the nature of his country around him, as the artist found in the flowers and plants of his country a rich source from which to draw inspiration from elements. His artistic style, and among the most important flowers that the artist preferred in this region were carnations, roses, pine, pomegranate, irises, and osprey

Carnation flower

Lotus flower

Cotton flower

Sunflower flower

Grape leaves and bunches

Pomegranate fruits

Fees for wheat ears

